

RAPID, BASIN-WIDE SURVEYING OF LARGE UNDERSEA
TOPOGRAPHY USING SCATTERED ACOUSTIC ENERGY

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Abstract

An acoustic experimental and processing technique is under development to provide rapid, wide-area reconnaissance of large undersea topography. The technique uses explosive sources and a commercial seismic array receiver to obtain topographic reverberation data covering radial distances of over 500 n.mi. After filtering and beamforming, the processing provides spatial stabilization of beams and averaging over multiple shots to correct for left-right ambiguities and to create basin-wide mappings of the major scatterers. The concept is illustrated using data from two basin areas, one northeast of New Zealand, and the other in the Canary Basin. The resultant latitude/longitude display of the location and strength of major scatterers reveals both known and uncharted features. The technique is intended to both complement other remote sensing techniques such as magnetics and altimetry, as well as provide initial reconnaissance results to guide more detailed survey operations. We discuss preliminary analysis to quantify the size of major topographic features from the level of their scattered return.

Introduction

Research is underway at the Naval Research Laboratory to evaluate an acoustic experimental and processing technique for rapid reconnaissance of entire ocean basin regions for large scale topography such as seamounts. This technique uses acoustic energy from explosive sources to ensonify the ocean basin region and a towed seismic streamer type receiver array to detect the basin reverberation. Computer processing of the receiver output enables detection of backscattered energy from undersea topography as a function of bearing to ranges of over 500 n.mi. from the towed receiver. Further processing permits mapping of the locations of all major topographic backscatterers in a latitude/longitude format. The reverberation data from repeated explosive shots at different locations and receiver orientations are combined to synthesize a clear map of major basin topography over an area in excess of 10^6 n.mi.². The data for such a map can be acquired over the relatively short span of about one week. In this paper we describe the experimental technique, processing scheme, and resulting reverberation maps using data from two ocean basin areas, one located about 500 n.mi. northeast of New Zealand and the other located about 1000 n.mi.

southwest of Gibraltar. We also describe preliminary work on the extraction of information about seamount heights from the reverberation maps. The reverberation mapping technique is complementary to other techniques for wide area mapping of major ocean bottom topography such as spacecraft altimetry¹ and aeromagnetic methods². The NRL mapping technique is being developed as a means for rapid, wide area surveying of remote ocean basins which have previously not been extensively mapped and is expected to indicate regions which may warrant further examination by high resolution, but relatively narrow area coverage techniques such as side scan sonar³. The technique described in this paper has spatial resolution of a few n.mi. or finer and represents a significant advance over earlier work in long range reverberation mapping⁴⁻⁷.

Experimental Reverberation Technique

The two major components of the NRL basin mapping technique are an explosive acoustic source and a horizontal towed seismic type receiver array. Both source and receiver are launched from a single vessel moving at nominal speed of 4 to 5 kt. The explosive sources are dropped at intervals of a few hours and are pressure detonated beneath the receiver array to maintain an approximately monostatic geometry. We have employed two configurations of explosive acoustic sources. During our reverberation mapping tests in a basin about 500 n.mi. northeast of New Zealand⁸ in 1976 and 1979, we used individual omnidirectional charges of about 23 kg (50 lb) TNT-equivalent. These sources worked well and provided sufficient energy in this relatively low ocean ambient noise environment to permit recording of reverberation from seamounts to over 500 n.mi. at all bearings from the receiver. During the 1980 test in the Canary Basin, we deployed vertical line arrays of small explosive charges, connected by primercord, to direct energy vertically (12° above the horizontal). This enables higher on-axis energy levels to overcome higher ocean ambient noise levels and there is less energy lost to the bottom at near ranges than for omnidirectional explosive charges. During the intervals between source detonations the outputs of the receiver hydrophones are recorded on magnetic tape while the vessel tows along a linear track.

Reverberation Data Processing

The recorded hydrophone data is processed to average into spectral bands and to perform beamforming. The procedure of averaging into spectral bands enables us to take advantage of the fact that the energy from the explosive shot detonations is broadband with periodic maxima at the source bubble frequency and its harmonics⁸. The procedure of beamforming⁸⁻¹¹ enables us to resolve the long range reverberation from basin topography into its associated bearing relative to the linear receiver towing direction. Typically we can resolve large scale topography variations of about 1 to 3 n.mi. in transverse extent at 100 n.mi. range from our receiver. The temporal averaging of directional reverberation estimates was generally 2 seconds or less thus enabling us to achieve a radial range resolution of 1 n.mi. or finer for the recordings from individual shot detonations. An important next step in the processing of the directional reverberation data is the spatial stabilization of the beam-time estimates for each shot since the receiving array orientation fluctuates by up to a few degrees during the time of the recordings due to slight variations in ship's speed and undersea currents. For each of our tests we have recorded navigation and array heading information and in some instances have used a moored continuously transmitting narrowband acoustic beacon source to track array orientation. Using information thus obtained on receiver array heading we compute the true bearing for our reverberation beam-time estimates on an instantaneous basis.

Ocean Basin Reverberation Maps

Once the directional reverberation data for each shot have been spatially stabilized as described above it is then relatively straightforward to transform these digital data into basin reverberation maps in a latitude/longitude format. Since the originating location of each shot is known from the navigation records and the receiver array headings are known we next perform the coordinate transformation into the map plane. We assume a mean nominal sound speed of 1500 m/s for our transformation from time to range. The resulting individual shot maps cover an ocean basin area over 10^6 n.mi.² (over 1000 n.mi. on a side). Since the acoustic energy suffers considerable propagation loss out to ranges of interest (over 500 n.mi.) we have used the NRL reverberation ray trace model¹² to compute mean transmission loss vs. range. Our computed estimates of propagation loss are then applied along with simple geometric estimates of scattering area and known estimates of source levels¹³ for our explosive sources to compute range independent backscattering strengths for the reverberation data of each individual shot map. Also, since our receiver is a linear array the reverberation from each seamount or other topographic feature appears twice on each single shot scattering strength map. Due to this left-right ambiguity we do not know, based only on one single shot reverberation map, which of the two reverberation signatures corresponds to a real geographic feature. During the course of the test, however, the receiver towing direction was changed in a prescribed fashion. In

all shot maps the true image of each topographic entity will appear at a fixed latitude/longitude, whereas the position of the false image will depend on array orientation. Hence, in order to resolve these spatial ambiguities we have developed an analysis technique for integrating single shot scattering strength maps into a composite basin-wide scattering strength map for each test area. We present a composite basin-wide scattering strength reverberation map for the test area northeast of New Zealand in Figure 1. This map is a composite representing an integration over several hundred individual shot maps from both the 1976 and 1979 tests. It shows the locations of major topographic scatterers in an area which is over 1000 n.mi. on a side. Both known and previously uncharted topographic features appear in this map. (See Figure 1 caption for description of topography.) In Figure 2 we present a preliminary scattering strength map based on 12 shots for our eastern Atlantic test of 1980. (See Figure 2 caption for identification of major topography.)

Seamount Height Estimation From Reverberation

In addition to mapping the positions of major topography over an entire ocean basin we are developing analysis techniques to apply to our long range reverberation data in order to extract information about seamount heights. We have performed a preliminary comparison of backscattering strengths with archival bathymetry data from the NORDA SYNBAPS data base¹⁴. We chose 6 radials from our single shot maps for the eastern Atlantic for this comparison. We find that seamount backscattering strengths are well correlated with seamount heights and have expressed this result in Figure 3.

Summary

We have described efforts in progress at the Naval Research Laboratory to develop an acoustic reverberation-based method for rapid basin-wide reconnaissance of large scale undersea topography. Our technique uses explosive sound sources and a seismic type receiver, both deployed from a single vessel. With sources detonated at typical intervals about 4 hours, and the resulting basin reverberation recorded from topography to radial ranges of over 500 n.mi., we are able to collect sufficient data in about a week's time to permit us to map all major scatterers in the basin. The resulting scattering strength maps are typically over 1000 n.mi. on a side. Preliminary analysis of our reverberation map data shows that we are able not only to locate seamounts and other geographic features in a basin, but are able to estimate seamount heights to at least + 500 m as well. Our reverberation technique complements other remote sensing methods such as space-craft altimetry and aeromagnetics and promises to be very useful for surveying remote ocean basin areas which to date have not been adequately surveyed, and will be helpful in determining areas worthy of inspection with more conventional high resolution mapping techniques.

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Figure 1. Integrated ocean basin scattering strength map for NRL Reverberation Tests of 1976, 1979 in south Pacific (approx. 1100 n.mi. x 1100 n.mi.). The Louisville Ridge appears on the eastern side of the basin. The Kermadec Wall and the rise towards New Zealand's North Island appear on the western side. Contour maps available at the time of these tests showed the Louisville Ridge as a mostly continuous ridge whereas our reverberation map indicates the presence of numerous discrete but adjacent seamounts. In addition, several isolated seamounts including the one at 37°S, 171°W were previously uncharted. Subsequent soundings by the New Zealand Navy have verified that the topography is essentially as shown above.

Figure 2. Integrated ocean basin scattering strength map for NRL Reverberation Test of 1980 in eastern Atlantic (1280 n.mi. x 1280 n.mi.). Range of grayscale is from -30 dB (darkest) to -60 dB (lightest). X's denote shot locations. Lettered features are identified as follows: (A) Great Meteor Seamount; (B) Hyeres, Irving, Cruiser Seamounts; (C) seamount; (D) East Azores Fracture Zone Rise; (E) seamount; (F) seamount; (G) Josephine Seamount; (H) Unicorn, Seine Seamounts; (I) Dragon Seamount; (J) Madeira Islands; (K) seamount group/ Dacia Seamount; (L) Salvage Island; (M) through (N) Canary Islands; (O) Echo Seamount; (P) Papp Seamount; (Q) Tropic Seamount; (R) seamount.

Figure 3. Reverberation-estimated seamount height vs. NORDA SYNAPS bathymetry height relative to nominal 5500 m bottom depth. These results indicate that we are able to estimate seamount heights to within \pm 500 m from our long range reverberation data. This compares favorably with height estimation accuracy of other techniques such as aeromagnetics and spacecraft altimetry.